

Augmented Reality on Students' Interest in Mathematics in Secondary Schools, Rivers State

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17237845>

Abstract

This study employed a descriptive survey design to examine Augmented Reality on students' interest in Mathematics, Rivers State. Two research questions guided this study. The population of the study was four thousand six hundred and fifty (4650) students. A purposive sampling technique was used to collate a sample size of one hundred (100) students for this study. The validated instrument used was Students Interest on Augmented Reality in Mathematics Inventory (SIARMI). Data collected were answered using descriptive statistic of mean and standard deviation. The study revealed high interest of students in learning with augmented reality in Mathematics in secondary schools. It equally revealed that the interest of female students while learning with augmented reality was higher than those of their male counterparts. It was recommended that: Mathematics teachers should integrate augmented reality into their lessons, as this approach can enhance students' grasp of Mathematics concepts and contribute to enhance students' interest. Mathematics teachers should ensure that both male and female students have equal access to the augmented reality approach in their classes. Doing so will enhance learning and bridge gender disparities.

Keywords: Augmented Reality, students' Interest, Mathematics Students.

Introduction

The integration of technology through digitalization in education has revolutionized traditional learning paradigms. Digitalization provides the technological foundation for Augmented Reality (AR), including hardware, software, and internet connectivity. Digitalization enables the creation and dissemination of digital content, which augmented reality can leverage to enhance learning experiences. Augmented reality uses digital content to create immersive, interactive learning practices that involve students and encourage deeper understanding, its interactive nature fosters student engagement, motivation, and participation. The use of digitalization through augmented reality can transform learning experiences, making them more effective, engaging, and relevant.

Augmented Reality (AR) denote a technology that incorporate real world with virtual elements such as graphics, sounds, and sensory input on the user's view of the physical world. Unlike Virtual Reality (VR), that plunges the user in a completely virtual environment, AR blends the real worlds and digital, allowing users to interact with both simultaneously. In the context of education, AR offers a novel approach to teaching and learning by engaging students in interactive, immersive experiences that facilitate better comprehension of complex concepts. AR applications typically work through devices such as smartphones, tablets, and AR glasses, which allow learners to interact with three-dimensional visualizations, simulations, and models in real time. These interactive

experiences engage students in learning by encouraging exploration, experimentation, and problem-solving, which are key elements of the constructivist learning theory (Chen, 2018).

Augmented reality, a cutting-edge technology, transforms digital content into the real world, generating interactive and engaging learning experiences. The integration of technology in education is offering students and educators innovative methods to achieve academic goals. Among these advancements, Augmented Reality (AR) stands out as a transformative tool. AR overlays digital content, such as 3D models, videos, and interactive simulations, onto the real-world environment. This blending of virtual and physical elements has the potential to redefine how students interact with educational materials, making learning more engaging, immersive, and effective (Bacca et al., 2014). For decades, education relied heavily on static materials like textbooks and one-dimensional visual aids. While effective to some degree, these methods often failed to engage students actively. AR transforms this scenario by enabling interactive learning environments. Students can, for instance, explore the solar system in 3D, manipulate celestial bodies, and observe planetary movements, fostering a deeper understanding of astronomical concepts (Wu et al., 2013).

Immediate feedback is another key feature of Augmented reality (AR) that boosts error-free performance. When students make mistakes while using AR applications, they receive corrective guidance in real time. This iterative learning process adopts an improved mentality, inspiring students to accept mistakes as chances for improvement rather than failures (Ibáñez & Delgado-Kloos, 2018). For instance, language learning applications using AR allow students to practice conversations in simulated environments, providing instant feedback on pronunciation and grammar.

One of Augmented reality's most transformative effects lies in its ability to simplify complex and abstract concepts. For instance, STEM education has long been considered challenging due to the abstract nature of many topics. AR offers interactive and visual representations of concepts that make them more accessible. A study by Dunleavy and Dede (2014) showed that students learning science concepts through AR outperformed those taught through traditional methods. Augmented Reality applications allow students to separate virtual organisms, observe cellular processes, and understand biological systems without the need for physical specimens. Similarly, in history education, AR recreates historical events and environments, enabling students to "walk through" ancient civilizations and witness key events as if they were there (Bacca et al., 2014). These experiences not only enhance understanding but also make learning memorable. Augmented Reality also has the potential to make education more inclusive. Students with disabilities can benefit immensely from AR tools. For example, visually impaired students can use AR applications that convert text into speech or provide tactile simulations, allowing them to access content independently. Similarly, AR enhances learning for students with cognitive disabilities by breaking down information into digestible, interactive components (Wu et al., 2013). Augmented reality also supports differentiated instruction, adapting to students' learning paces. Applications can assess a student's current knowledge level and customize content accordingly, ensuring that all learners receive appropriate challenges and support. This adaptability addresses one of the longstanding issues in education meeting the diverse needs of every student in the classroom.

The integration of Augmented Reality into education offers unparalleled opportunities to enhance academic performance. By creating immersive, engaging, and inclusive learning environments, Augmented Reality may have the potential to transform traditional education systems. Its ability to boost motivation, simplify complex concepts, and support diverse learners makes it a valuable tool

for the 21st-century classroom. However, realizing its full potential requires overcoming barriers related to low academic performance of students, cost, infrastructure, and training. With strategic investments and collaboration, Augmented Reality can become a cornerstone of modern education, preparing students for a rapidly evolving world. According to, Agreeing, Smart (2006), asserts that” Once students generate interest in a subject and are excited about learning the subject, half of the problem would have been solved”. Therefore, there is need to consider students interest with augmented reality.

Lowman (2017) defined interest as a relatively stable psychological characteristic of people which identify the personal evaluation (subjective attributions of ‘goodness’ or ‘badness’) judged degree of personal fit or misfit attached to particular groups of occupational or leisure activity clusters. Research has demonstrated that the interest towards Physics, changes with exposure to Physics and its related activities. Obiefuna, Okoro and Iwuamaji, (2010) explained that interest remains a very vital point a teacher must also consider to ensure effective teaching and learning and to boost performance. The situation worsens where careers in physics are imposed on children without the interest of the learner (student). The teacher is expected to create and sustain interest in the learner. Interest deals with likes, dislikes and emotional disposition. Interest arrests the attention of the learner in a teaching-learning situation. When a child (learner) has interest in what is taught (Mathematics), there is that tendency to learn more and more. This could propel the learner to do work independently; thereby reading beyond what is taught in class, wanting to excel, desiring to be punctual to school and to participate in classroom activities (simulation activities, practical lessons).

With a review of some empirical findings, Bower et al. (2017), examined the effects of AR and students’ learning outcomes in geometry. The study concluded that AR-supported learning activities enhanced students’ ability to solve geometric problems, improving both their understanding of geometric principles and their performance on related assessments. The students who used AR had significantly higher scores in post-tests compared to their peers who were taught using traditional methods. These results suggest that AR can support students in comprehending abstract mathematical concepts, making them more concrete and tangible.

Similarly, Cheng and Tsai (2013) explored the potential of AR to enhance students’ understanding of calculus concepts. Their findings indicated that AR-based learning interventions enabled students to visualize complex functions and their transformations, leading to improved problem-solving skills and academic performance. The authors emphasized the benefit of AR in supporting students with diverse learning styles by providing visual and interactive representations of mathematical concepts.

In a study by Wu et al. (2013), the researchers examined how AR impacted students’ understanding of algebra. The findings showed that students who engaged in AR-assisted lessons demonstrated a deeper understanding of algebraic equations and relationships. The AR environment provided them with the opportunity to visualize algebraic expressions and manipulate variables in real time, which contributed to better learning outcomes. This study highlights the power of AR in making abstract algebraic concepts more accessible to students by providing them with interactive tools to explore and engage with the material.

Dunleavy and Dede (2014) conducted a study in which they integrated AR into secondary school classrooms to assess its impact on students’ engagement with mathematics. The study revealed that students showed a higher level of engagement and motivation when learning through AR-based activities. The interactive nature of AR allowed students to explore mathematical concepts in a more

hands-on and engaging way, increasing their interest and enthusiasm for the subject. This heightened engagement, in turn, led to improved academic performance in mathematics.

Additionally, Bacca et al. (2014) upheld a review on the use of AR in classroom and found that AR had a positive impact on students' motivation, particularly in subjects that students traditionally find challenging, such as mathematics. The authors emphasized that the immersive and interactive features of AR allowed students to engage deeply with the content, making learning more enjoyable and effective. This engagement was linked to higher levels of student achievement and improved problem-solving skills in mathematics.

Huang et al. (2016) also explored the role of AR in increasing student motivation and engagement in a mathematics classroom. The study found that students who used AR to explore geometrical concepts demonstrated greater enthusiasm and participation in lessons compared to students taught through traditional methods. The interactive, hands-on nature of AR allowed students to visualize and manipulate geometric shapes, which increased their interest in the subject and motivated them to engage more actively in learning activities.

In a study by Huang and Liaw (2018), the researchers found insignificant gender difference via academic performance of male and its counterpart students when applying AR for learning mathematics. Both genders showed similar levels of improvement in their understanding of mathematical concepts and problem-solving abilities. However, the study highlighted that female student, in particular, reported a more positive attitude towards using AR in learning, suggesting that AR may be more motivating for female students in mathematics education.

Similarly, Cheng and Tsai (2013) found that AR-based learning did not lead to significant differences via academic performance base on students' gender in calculus. Though, female students tended to exhibit greater interest and engagement in the AR lessons, which could have long-term benefits for their performance in mathematics. This finding suggests that AR could be particularly effective in motivating female students who may traditionally struggle with mathematics.

Mathematics with its abstract and often challenging nature, stands to benefit significantly from the application of Augmented Reality (AR) technologies. Empirical research stated above shows that students' engagement and motivation improve when AR is used in teaching mathematics. This may be true in secondary school education, where students begin to encounter more complex topics in subjects like algebra, geometry, and calculus. Traditional methods of teaching these subjects often rely heavily on textbooks and 2D diagrams, which can be difficult for students to fully comprehend. AR, on the other hand, allows students to interact with 3D models, visualizing and manipulating mathematical structures in real-time.

Several studies have considered the impact of instruction methods on students' achievement in science. According to research, inactive or ineffective teaching methods can significantly contribute to low performance in mathematics. Studies have shown that traditional teaching methods can be ineffective in promoting student engagement and understanding. In contrast, interactive and student-centered approaches can lead to better learning outcomes. Also, a study by Tshabalala and Ncube (2016) found that students' poor performance in mathematics can be attributed to ineffective teaching methods. Similarly, Enu, Agyman, and Nkum (2015) identified teaching methods as a significant factor influencing students' mathematics performance.

Research emphasizes the importance of interactive learning experiences in mathematics education. This can include approaches such as technology integration. Unlike the traditional methods regarded as the reason behind the low performance of students as the majority of teachers relied on

it, which often emphasize rote memorization, Augmented Reality encourages active participation. Through visual, auditory, and kinesthetic interactions, it caters to diverse learning styles, ensuring inclusivity in classrooms (Ibáñez & Delgado-Kloos, 2018). For example, in subjects like Mathematics, AR allows students to visualize geometrical structures and parametric equations in real time, bridging the gap between abstract theory and tangible experience.

However, the findings of Mine and Yusuf (2013) Sukran, Asiye and Suleyman (2015) on “origami-based instruction” revealed that origami-based instruction, employing creative teaching of Mathematics and teaching Mathematics manipulatively increase Mathematics achievement and positive interest towards Mathematics.

The findings of, Kebin and Gamage (2022) revealed that students are highly interested in origami instructional strategy classrooms than those in the conventional teaching classrooms

Considering gender in Students interest, the findings by, Ugwuadu (2011) found out that students taught biology using the dialogic, peer and teacher guided discourse patterns did not differ significantly from one another in their interest; there is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female students taught biology with each of the three discourse patterns.

Also, the findings of, Stephen (2013) on “assessing the effect of instructional model known as dynamic software on gender” opined that instructional model was not more important as other factors in driving students’ interest and attitudes, that instead grades and teachers’ attitudes played a great role in determining students’ interest and attitudes than laboratory method.

However, Wonu and Anackwe (2014) found out that there was no significant difference in the mathematic achievement of male and female students.

Therefore, the point is that would this Augmented Reality enhance students’ interest in Mathematics in Secondary Schools, Rivers State?

Objective of the Study

This study investigated augmented reality on students’ interest in Mathematics in Secondary Schools, Rivers State, specifically; this study addresses its objectives as follows:

1. To evaluate the level of augmented reality on students' interest in Mathematics in Secondary Schools.
2. To assess the interest of students on augmented reality based on gender.

Research Questions

1. What is the interest of students on augmented reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools?
2. What is the interest of male and female students on augmented reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools?

Methods

The descriptive survey design was used to determine the interest of students on Augmented Reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools. The population of the study was four thousand six hundred and fifty (4650) students. A purposive random sampling technique was used to collate a sample size of one hundred (100) students for this study. Purposive sampling technique was used purposely to pick only schools that have Mathematics laboratories, projectile and laptops that were considered and used for this study. The instrument used was the Students Interest in Augmented Reality in Mathematics Inventory (SIARMI). The reliability of the instrument (SIARMI) was determined using a test-retest method on data collection and a Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) method was used to test for the reliability of the instrument (SIARMI) and a reliable value of 0.81 was obtained. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions.

Result and data Presentation**Research Questions one**

What is the interest of students on augmented reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools? **Table 1: The mean and standard deviation on interest scores of students on augmented reality.**

s/no	Items	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD(1)	Mean	SD
1	I find Mathematics lessons more engaging when augmented reality (AR) is used	70	13	6	11	3.42	1.10
2	AR technology makes complex Mathematics concepts easier to understand	62	11	5	22	3.13	1.21
3	I would like to use AR more frequently in my Mathematics classes.	67	10	7	16	3.28	1.14
4	AR enhances my interest in science subjects	66	8	8	18	3.22	1.01
5	I enjoy exploring Mathematics concepts through interactive AR experiences	71	12	0	17	3.37	1.11
Grand mean						3.28	1.10

Table 1: showed that items (1 to 5) had means which were greater than the criterion mean (2.50). Moreover, the grand mean (**3.28**) was also greater than the criterion means. This established that there was a high interest of students on learning with augmented reality in secondary schools.

Research Questions two

What is the interest of male and female students on augmented reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools?

Table 2: The mean and standard deviation on interest of male and female students on augmented reality

s/no	Items	Male		Female	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	I find Mathematics lessons more engaging when augmented reality (AR) is used	3.12	1.10	3.52	1.10
2	AR technology makes complex Mathematics concepts easier to understand	3.00	1.21	3.21	1.21
3	I would like to use AR more frequently in my Mathematics classes.	3.11	1.14	3.31	1.14
4	AR enhances my interest in Mathematics subjects	3.02	1.01	3.42	1.01
5	I enjoy exploring Mathematics concepts through interactive AR experiences	3.17	1.11	3.38	1.11
Grand mean		3.1	1.11	3.3	1.12

Table 2: showed that items (1 to 5) had means which were greater than the criterion mean (2.50). Moreover, the grand means (**3.1**) for male and (**3.3**) for female were also greater than the criterion means, this implies that both sexes had high interest while learning with augmented reality. The grand means scores also established that female (**3.3**) student had high interest on augmented reality than the male (**3.1**) students in learning with augmented reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Augmented Reality and Students' interest in Mathematics

Results in table 1 revealed high interest of students in learning with augmented reality in Mathematics in secondary schools. The finding of this study is in synonym with the findings of, Kebin and Gamage (2022) whose findings revealed that students are highly interested in origami instructional strategy classrooms than those in the conventional teaching classrooms.

This finding also supported the findings of, Sukran, Asiye and Suleyman (2015), who revealed that origami-based instruction, employing creative teaching of Mathematics, teaching Mathematics manipulatively increase Mathematics achievement and positive interest towards Mathematics. The finding is in consonance with the theories of: Bandura (1997), who proposed that an individual is more inclined to receive a displayed conduct on the off chance that it is in results they valued.

This finding opposed the findings of Stephen and Schusslev (2013), who revealed that instructional model was not more important as other factors in driving students' interest and attitudes, that instead grades and teachers' attitudes played a great role in determining students' interest and attitudes than laboratory.

Students Gender in Interest with Augmented Reality.

The results in tables 2 revealed that the interest of female students while learning with augmented reality was higher than those of the interest of their male counterparts.

This finding is in agreement with the research by, Kebin and Gamage (2022), the findings revealed gender difference on students learning with origami instructional strategy in mathematics classrooms.

This finding opposed the findings of Olaf, Jurgen and Kai (2010) involving 602 students in Germany, opined that gender differences in achievement in favour of boys in mathematics achievement, it also found out that interest had no significant effect on learning from grade 7 to grade 10 but affected their course selection.

This result disagrees with the findings of, Ugwuadu (2011) who found no significant difference in the compared mean interest scores of male and female students taught biology concepts using the dialogue discuss pattern.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that the use of augmented reality enhances students' interest in Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Rivers State. It also revealed that female students had a higher interest compare to male students while learning with augmented reality in Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Recommendation

The findings of this study were recommended based on the following:

1. Mathematics teachers should integrate augmented reality into their lessons, as this approach can enhance students' grasp of Mathematics concepts and contribute to enhance students' interest.
2. Mathematics teachers should ensure that both male and female students have equal access to the augmented reality approach in their lessons. Doing so will enhance performance for all students and bridge the gap in gender disparities.

References

- Bacca, J., Baldiris, S., Fabregat, R., Graf, S., & Kinshuk. (2014). Augmented Reality Trends in Education: A Systematic Review of Research and Applications. *Educational Technology & Society*, 17(4), 133-149.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. General Learning Press.
- Bower, M., Howe, C., McCredie, N., Robinson, A., & Grover, D. (2017). Augmented Reality in Education – Cases, Places, and Potentials. *Educational Media International*, 54(1), 1-15.
- Chen, C. M. (2018). The Effectiveness of Using Augmented Reality to Enhance Mathematics
- Cheng, K. H., & Tsai, C. C. (2013). Affordances of Augmented Reality in Science Learning:
- Dunleavy, M., & Dede, C. (2014). Augmented Reality Teaching and Learning. In *Handbook of Research on Educational Communications and Technology* (pp. 735-745). Springer.
- Enu, J., Agyman, O., & Nkum, D. (2015). Factors influencing students' mathematics performance in some selected colleges of education in Ghana. *International Journal of Education and Learning Development*, 3(3), 68–74. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-3-3-1>.
- Huang, H. M., & Liaw, S. S. (2018). Exploring learners' attitudes toward learning in AR environments. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 26(2), 199-214.
- Huang, L., Jiang, J. H., Murray, L. T., Damon, M. R., Su, H., & Livesey, N. J. (2016). Evaluation of UTLS carbon monoxide simulations in GMI and GEOS-Chem chemical transport models using Aura MLS observations. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 16(11), 5641– 5663. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-16-5641-2016>.

- Ibáñez, M.-B., & Delgado-Kloos, C. (2018). Augmented Reality for STEM Learning: A Systematic Review. *Computers & Education*, 123, 109-123.
- Kebin, O. B. & Gamage, T. (2022) Effect of Origami Instructional Strategy on Students' interest in Geometry, *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Theorists & Educational Technologists (NJOCTET)*, 7(1). 133-145.
- Obiefuna, C. A., Okoro. F. & Iwuamaji F. N (2010). *Basic principles and methods of teaching and learning*. Owerri. Career publishers.
- Sedanur, C., Mine, I., & Yusuf, K. (2013) Investigating effect of origami-based instruction, on elementary students spatial skills and perceptions. *Journal of educational research*, 107(1), 59-68.
- Suggestions for Future Research. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 22(4), 449–462.
- Sukran, T., Asiye, B., & Suleyman, K. (2015) The Effects of Teaching Mathematics creatively on academic achievement, attitudes towards mathematics, and Mathematics anxiety. *International Journal of innovation in science and mathematics education*, 23(4), 24. Retrieved from; openjournals.library.usyd.edu.au/index.php/CAL/article/viewFile/7887/10018.
- Tshabalala, T., & Ncube, A. C. (2016). Causes of poor performance of ordinary level pupils in mathematics in rural secondary schools in Nkayi District: Learner's attributions. *Nova Journal of Medical and Biological Sciences*, 1(1), 4–14. <https://doi.org/10.12691/njmsb-1-1-1>.
- Ugwuadu, O.R. (2011). Effects of Discourse Patterns on Students' Achievement and Learning. *Educational Technology & Society*, 21(4), 123–134.
- Wonu, N. & Anaekwe, E. (2014). School effect on students' mathematical achievement in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 4 (1) 69-77.
- Wu, H.-K., Lee, S. W. Y., Chang, H.-Y., & Liang, J.-C. (2013). Current Status, Opportunities, and Challenges of Augmented Reality in Education. *Computers & Education*, 62, 41–49.